

D4.4 Report and recommendations on FAIR incentives and expected impacts in the Nordics, Baltics and EOSC

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Abstract

This deliverable describes ways of developing a FAIR research culture based on incentives. It explores the existing incentive structures in place for FAIR research practices in the Nordics and Baltics, and promotes additional efficient incentives based on findings from a qualitative study using a multi-stakeholder approach. It also reflects on the expected impacts an increased level of FAIRness may have on the Nordic and Baltic research communities.

The deliverable starts by delineating the methodology used for exploring the FAIR incentives and the synergies made within the project. Next, the study findings are presented; starting with recommendations on how to achieve increased levels of FAIR uptake, followed by identified challenges to FAIR uptake, with both parts splitting into their own sets of incentive themes. One chapter is dedicated to the outcomes of community engagement and the last chapter addresses ways of accelerating the uptake of FAIR through incentives, both on a generic level, as well as split into tailor-made stakeholder recommendations and expected impact.

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I. Introduction

I.1 Background and objectives

The main ambition of this study is to encourage researchers to comply with FAIR data practices in their research. This is achieved by demonstrating the perceived impact and existing incentives for FAIR compliance. The multi-phased method started with a mapping exercise of already established FAIR policy incentives and any gaps impeding FAIR adoption. The next phase was devoted to a qualitative study, where the ambition was to reach out to scientists to get an insight into the FAIR incentives in place influencing their research work and whether these were considered to have a positive (incentivising) or negative (disincentivising) impact. In addition, we interviewed other stakeholders as well who either have an impact on how FAIR incentives are shaped or have an insight into the needs and demands of researchers and pain points in terms of research data management practices. The qualitative study provided us with a deeper insight into the current state of play and allowed us to identify the most well-received FAIR incentives in place, as well as the disincentivising ones. The final phase of the study was realised through community engagement, where a range of policymakers and community stakeholders participated in a workshop to seek further input on the findings and to harmonise policies on FAIR incentives in the region. The findings of the qualitative study combined with the input from the community stakeholder engagement provided us with the material needed to develop and suggest new efficient incentives to be proactively promoted and which will ultimately have a positive effect on FAIR compliance levels.

1.2 Relevant literature

In our landscaping study, we came across many reports and articles highlighting the importance and providing good examples of how FAIR and Open Science can contribute to the quality, trustworthiness and transparency of research when exploited to their fullest potential.

Many of the main objectives of the [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda \(SRIA\) of the European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#)¹ concur with our study; to convince scientists of making research data more accessible and open whenever possible, and that rich publications, data and software will enable machine-actionability. The report also sets out some guiding principles. The relevant ones for our study are supported in the following ones: communication with the researchers is fundamental to generating value, diversity in experiences related to FAIR and Open Science is understood and should be taken into account when planning services, infrastructure, recommendations etc., multi-stakeholder approach is crucial for driving changes in research, research is to be open by default, and the importance of supporting and enabling the generation of FAIR research artefacts.

To achieve all of this, the critical success factors as set out by the SRIA are:

- for researchers to make relevant results available as openly as possible,

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/935288>

- data stewards to be installed to support researchers in being Open Science compliant,
- researchers to be incentivised to conduct Open Science,
- research data to be made FAIR by design, and for research to be increasingly discoverable and reusable across disciplines.

We can also find useful references for our work in the report [Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice by the FAIR in practice task force of the European open science cloud FAIR working group](#)². Based on the report, there are various issues why FAIR is not implemented in practice. Most relevant for our study are the ones on technical barriers - lack of repositories, capability to deal with big or complex data, interoperability and (disciplinary) metadata issues, and social barriers - FAIR is confusing and hard to implement on data, lack of sufficient benefits (recognition) and resources (funding and time), resistance to share data, and lack of knowledge on copyright, legal issues and FAIR in general.

To address these challenges, the report offers six recommendations:

1. Fund awareness-raising, training, education and community-specific support,
2. Fund development, adoption and maintenance of community standards, tools, and infrastructure,
3. Incentivise development of community governance,
4. Translate FAIR guidelines for other digital objects,
5. Reward and recognise improvements of FAIR practice,
6. Develop and monitor adequate policies for FAIR data and research objects.

The report [Perspectives on the future of open science. Effects of global variation in open science practices on the European research system](#)³ looks at how the Open Science initiatives should be driven forward and lists the drivers pushing things forwards, as well as the barriers slowing things down. Drivers can be seen as incentives and barriers as disincentives. Some of the Open Science drivers presented in the report are: giving credit for OS practices, making OS compliance easier by making adequate tools and services available, raising awareness of OS, and incentivising the reuse of research outputs. Some barriers to Open Science listed in the report are lack of credit, cost, and time issues accompanied with data sharing, worries about data misuse, lack of skills, and insufficiency of socio-economic benefits of OS. We also found support for these claims in our quantitative study on FAIR incentives.

To make it really clear how our recommendations on FAIR incentives and the goals set out to achieve these relate to changes necessary to make FAIR happen, we decided to make use of the Center for Open Science theory of change model presented in the report Strategy for Culture Change⁴.

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice by the FAIR in practice task force of the European open science cloud FAIR working group*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/986252>

³ Hessels, L., Koens, L., Diederens, P. (2021). *Perspectives on the future of open science : effects of global variation in open science practices on the European research system*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/054281>

⁴ Nosek, B. (11 June, 2019). *Strategy for culture change*. Center for Open Science. <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>

This developed theory of research culture change (Nosek, 2019) uses a pyramid to represent five levels of intervention for a research culture change that can be adapted for FAIR data implementation (figure 1). The Pyramid of the Cultural Change of Research reveals that the term encompasses a wide range of important activities that must occur for the cultural shift to happen. As shown in Nosek's pyramid, each activity makes FAIR data implementation possible, easy, normative, rewarding, and required. Infrastructure, user experience, communities, incentives, and policy are all important and must be coordinated. Levels of the pyramid are progressive, implying that the successful implementation of higher levels depends on the successful implementation of lower levels. It is easier to make it rewarding or implement policy when the infrastructure and user experience/know-how is strong. You cannot make something mandatory if you do not have the infrastructure or experience to carry it out. The model shows that each level plays an important role and only combined can make a real impact and cultural shift.

Figure 1: Theory of change model (Nosek B., 2019)

People, and how they adapt to new ideas, need to be considered for a cultural shift to happen. Diffusion of innovation theory⁵ (figure 2) by Everett Rogers shows adopter categories and how people tend to accept innovations. The categories are innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. This theory combined with Nosek's pyramid shows what kind of motivation drives each category. In subchapter [5.3.2 Theory of change model and diffusion of innovation theory](#) these models are analysed.

⁵ Boston University School of Public Health. (2019). *Behavioral change models. Diffusion of Innovation Theory.* https://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/MPH-Modules/SB/BehavioralChangeTheories/BehavioralChangeTheories4.html#headingtaglink_1

Figure 2: Diffusion of innovation theory (Roggers, E., 1962)¹²

Awareness-raising is needed. According to data from [The State of Open Data 2021 report](#)⁶ 34% of the 2021 survey respondents had never heard of FAIR principles, and 38% had heard of but were not familiar with the FAIR principles.

To raise awareness, research administration and support need to engage researchers. LIBER Research Data Management Working Group gives six practical guidelines (pillars)⁷ for this:

1. Employ an Institutional Policy,
2. Personally Engage with the Research Community,
3. Engage Early-Career Researchers,
4. Facilitate Researcher-to-Researcher Communication via Data Stewards,
5. Offer RDM Services and Training,
6. Communicate Everything You Do.

The fact that there is not one main activity, but many interdependent activities can also be seen in [UNESCO's discussions of Open Science implementation](#)⁸. The main activities depicted are (figure 3):

- Fostering a culture of Open Science
- Investing in infrastructure and services
- Promoting innovative approaches
- Promoting a common understanding
- Investing in human resources

⁶ Simons, N., Goodey, G., Hardeman, M., Clare, C., Gonzales, S. et al. (2021): *The State of Open Data 2021*. Digital Science. (Report). <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17061347.v1>; The survey data behind the report can be found at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17081231>.

⁷ Boserup Thestrup, J., Braskova, M. Krogh Kruuse, K. & Lembinen, L. (2020). *The 6 Pillars of Engaging Researchers in Research Data Management (RDM)*. LIBER RDM Working Group. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4475475>

⁸ The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.(2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

- Promoting cooperation
- Developing an enabling policy environment

The adaptation of research culture to Open Science practices is volatile. All activities are interconnected, and gears depict how one action can affect others, keeping the idea moving even if it is lagging in other areas.

Figure 3: UNESCO's Open Science - Areas of action model

1.3 Approach

We collected data for this report and recommendations on FAIR incentives in three phases (yellow boxes in [Figure 4](#)). At all phases, we collected data from key stakeholder groups (grey box in [Figure 4](#)). We present all findings from the data collection in a section of its own in the report (green box in [Figure 4](#)). Section two is a landscape analysis, mapping policies and reviewing existing incentives in the Nordic and Baltic countries. Section three describes the qualitative study approach used to grow our understanding of the needs and demands of researchers, and through that, we were able to identify effective incentives. In the third phase, stakeholders' feedback was gathered on the qualitative study results and the analysis is presented in section four. In section five, we make recommendations derived from the outcome of all three phases. Lastly, the expected impact of large-scale FAIR uptake is described.

Figure 4: EOSC-Nordic WP4 T4.3 subtasks and deliverable

2. Landscape analysis of policy-implemented incentives

2.1 Scope and objectives

The first step of the FAIR incentives study was to conduct a landscaping activity, where the task force mapped the existing policy and implemented FAIR incentives in the Nordic and Baltic countries. The main ambition of this study is to raise awareness of the developments ongoing in neighbouring countries. The awareness-raising effort is an efficient tool for change, as it points to best practices in the development of FAIR incentives and policies, and can be used as a reference model in the other participating countries. This exercise was done lightly, as very similar work had already been done by task 2.1 in WP2.

WP2, *Policies, legal issues and sustainability*, did an extensive landscape study, where they described any policy and similar documentation such as written guidelines, policies et.al. relating to specific focus areas. The study comprised the countries Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Norway, Latvia, Lithuania, and Sweden. The topics of the study were:

- Policy-implemented incentives for FAIR
- Policies for Open Science training/training for making data FAIR
- Policies for making other research objects FAIR
- Policies facilitating cross-border research

D2.5 Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries (second report)⁹ was published in early 2021 and at that time, a few of the Nordic and Baltic countries had policies or laws in place for incentivising uptake of FAIR practices. The policies were made by different types of stakeholders, such as funders, ministries, and libraries at Higher Education Institutions. The policies were increasingly also specifically addressing training on Open Science and FAIR research practices. In countries where there were no policies nor training provided on Open Science and FAIR, there was an increasing awareness of the importance and value of including training on Open Science and FAIR in the policies. However, Open Science training was provided in most of the inventoried countries. Only a minority of the countries had policies in place for making research objects FAIR, other than data and metadata. The report concluded that more regulatory documents on making other research objects FAIR would be needed to ensure transparency, reproducibility and reusability of research.

The most commonly represented elements are:

- Research Culture
- Open access to research publications
- Open access to data, data management & FAIR
- Preservation and reuse of scientific information

The least commonly represented elements are:

- Citizen science
- Open education & open access to educational resources

⁹ Hammargren, P-O., Arvola, M. & Rauste, P. (2021). *D2.5: Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries*. (EOSC Nordic second report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5537068>

- Open access to research data & methods

In addition to these, the other elements explored in the study are:

- Skills and competencies
- Incentives and rewards
- Infrastructures that include aspects of Open Science

The landscaping study continued where the former deliverable ended and provided a view of how the landscape had changed for around one year. The report D2.8 Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries (final report)¹⁰ had a heavier focus on developments around FAIR, also including guidelines on FAIR, in addition to national policies. The study found that a cost analysis is being made on data infrastructures in one of the countries (Denmark) and that two countries are making recommendations on open education (Estonia and Finland). In some countries, national funders are increasingly recommending FAIR-compliant research to be conducted with the funding they provide (Denmark, Estonia, Finland), and in Latvia and Norway, the national open science strategies highly recommend research to be FAIR compliant. Finland is advancing on Open Science and FAIR developments extensively and rapidly and has covered all of the elements included in the study.

D2.3, *Open Science in the Nordics: legal insights*, and D2.7, *Open Science in the Nordics: recommendations on legal issues*, deal with legal issues that may constitute proper or perceived obstacles to the uptake of Open Science.

2.2 Synergies within the project

Our findings offer various similarities to WP2 findings in D2.8. Both our and WP2 recommendations (recommendations 2, 3, 8 and 9) conclude that both national and international (regional and EU) policies and services should be interlinked and aligned to simplify the adoption of Open Science principles. In addition, the implementation of FAIR data and OS requires clear guidelines and directions (WP2 - Recommendation 5). Raising awareness among researchers in different stages of their careers is vital (WP2 - Recommendation 6) and should be a mandatory task for all stakeholders. Our study found that researchers require clear and permanent funding which helps them to comply with FAIRification of data in collaboration with other researchers, WP2's recommendations confirm this (Recommendations 6.2.1-4.).

Our work on FAIR incentives has received great interest among various stakeholder groups and has been presented in a workshop "*National policies relevant to EOSC deployment*" in Strasbourg organised by EOSC Future, EOSC Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, ExPaNDS, NI4OS, EOSC Synergy and FAIRsFAIR on 4 May. On 9 May, we organised a virtual workshop dedicated to relevant community stakeholders and policymakers in the Nordic

¹⁰ Hansson, E-L., Bukauskas, L., Garavelli, S., Gunnarsdóttir, B., Hammargren, P-O., Rosti, T., Hienola, A., Iozzi, M. F., Morthorst-Jensen, D. A. M., Christiansen, E., Rauste, P., Slaidins, I., & Vellemaa, T. (2022). *D2.8: Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries*. (EOSC Nordic final report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6503709>

and Baltic regions to further work on the findings retrieved from the qualitative study. See [chapter 4](#) for more information about the stakeholder workshop. Furthermore, the work has been presented at the 2022 NeIC Conference taking place in Oslo from 29 May-1 June.

3. Identifying incentives and challenges of FAIR

3.1 Methodology

The main ambition of this study is to encourage researchers to comply with FAIR data practices in their research. We achieve this by demonstrating the benefits and existing incentives in place for FAIR compliance. The task force on FAIR incentives used a qualitative study approach using semi-structured interviews to achieve this. The interviews allowed the task force to get experience-based input to the study, which is of high value when exploring incentives for doing research based on the FAIR Principles. Interview guides were established and tailor-made for each stakeholder group. However, the questions for all stakeholders included the following topics: background and connection to Open Science, practices of managing, sharing and reusing research data, research funding, FAIR reflections, and support services.

3.1.1 Sampling and interview procedure

Six stakeholder groups were identified and interviewed during the study:

- (1) researchers,
- (2) data stewards/research support at institutions (including librarians),
- (3) management personnel at universities,
- (4) research funders and representatives of the ministries for education and research,
- (5) national data services and

(6) legal advisors.

In total, 28 interviews were conducted and 29 people were interviewed (two respondents participated together in one interview), where the gender balance was 15 men and 14 women. 16 of the respondents were researchers and 13 represented the five other stakeholder groups (see table 1).

Table 1: The number of respondents per stakeholder group.

Stakeholder group	# Participants
Researchers	16
Research support at institutions	3
Management personnel at universities	2
Research funders and representatives of the ministries for education and research	5
National data services	2
Legal advisors	1
Total	29

The participants came from eight Nordic and Baltic countries. On average 3,6 interviews per country were held (see table 2).

Table 2: The average number of participants per country.

Country	# Participants
Denmark	3
Estonia	4
Finland	7
Iceland	2
Latvia	2
Lithuania	4
Norway	3
Sweden	4
The average number of interviews per country	3.6

Two-thirds of the researcher participants represented natural sciences, whereas one-third were from social sciences and humanities as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Different disciplines represented by researchers (categorised using the OECD Field of Science classification)¹¹.

OECD FOS classification	OECD FOS classification level 2	# Researchers
1. Natural sciences	1.3 Physical sciences	2
	1.4 Chemical sciences	2
	1.5 Earth and related Environmental sciences	5
	1.6 Biological sciences	1
1. Natural sciences subtotal		10
5. Social sciences	5.2 Economics and Business	1
	5.4 Sociology	1
	5.8 Media and communications	1
5. Social sciences subtotal		3
6. Humanities	6.2 Languages and Literature	3
6. Humanities subtotal		3
Grand total		16

Since the project partners come from eight Nordic and Baltic countries, the following factors were taken into consideration: country representation, gender balance, and at least half of the respondents had to be researchers. Members of the WP listed relevant stakeholders from their countries, and the interview group then contacted these stakeholders. Each participant was approached individually, and the purpose and process of the study were introduced during the scheduling. In general, interviews took place with one respondent and two interviewers; one person led the interview, while the other took notes.

The interviews were held between 28 June and 8 November 2021. Most interviews were held in English; however, there were a few exceptions where the interviews were held in the native language of the respondent and one interview took place with two respondents. The interviews took place in Zoom and were recorded. The recordings were summarised by the note-taker of the interview based on the notes and recording, reconfirmed by the interviewer and then sent for the final confirmation to the respondents. Recordings will not be made available and will be deleted after the project. Interviews held in languages other than English were transcribed and then summarised into English.

¹¹ OECD/OCDE. (2007). *Revised Field of Science and technology (FOS) Classification in the Frascati Manual*. <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>

3.1.2 Analysis of the interviews

An analysis task force analysed all interviews one by one and response by response. The primary analysis was done in a spreadsheet where the main ideas of each question were taken out. This spreadsheet was checked by various members of the analysis task force. The analysis task force had almost a thousand quotations to go through, of which five hundred came from researchers. These responses were then categorised and transferred to the software Atlas.ti where further cross-referencing and coding exercises took place. Codes and code groups were formed and analysis tools (e.g. networks, co-occurrence -tables, code-document -tables) of the software were used ([see appendices](#)). Results from Atlas.ti analysis were then shared with the entire analysis working group. Iterations were made in a few cases and coding in Atlas.ti was updated accordingly. Based on the results, further analysis was conducted: coding, incentives analysis, archetypes of FAIR adoption, and crosscheck analysis with previous findings and reports.

3.2 Results and key findings

3.2.1 Identified incentives

We identified seven FAIR incentive themes based on the interviews.

Offer additional resources for data curation and sharing (money and time) (i)

Additional resources are needed e.g. data curation for publishing purposes and data management. On the other hand, it also became evident in the interviews that data management and curation for publishing purposes should be an integral part of the everyday work of a researcher, but as resources are limited, incentives would help drive its case.

Funding, in general, was seen as a strong incentive, which effectively drives its case among researchers. Additional funding was also suggested to be granted following data publishing and that the units would receive money for openly published articles based on a funding distribution model.

Have a sustainable infrastructure in place for sharing and publishing data (ii)

Having a sustainable infrastructure for sharing and publishing data in place is crucial for advancing data management based on the FAIR principles. Sustainable domain-specific infrastructure for supporting research and machine-actionable metadata are important elements of a well-functioning research environment. Additionally, adequate technical support, skills and tools are needed for advancing FAIR data management.

Improve research support services and offer training (iii)

Researchers must be provided with high-quality research support services and training. This includes a central data management support service at their home organisations as well as legal support and guidance. Research projects need support in publishing data and ideally also a person in the project dedicated to tackling data management issues. Having data stewards (or data champions) in place is seen as an incentive and is perceived as a role model for FAIR data management. Data stewards could also assist researchers with machine-actionable metadata and persistent identifiers. Training, in general, is also seen as highly relevant to increasing FAIR compliance. Training new researcher generations about FAIR has an impact on future science as they are aware of requirements and used to be FAIR from the start of their research careers.

Develop data sharing metrics and a system based on merits (iv)

There is an imperative need to develop data-sharing metrics and a system based on merits for researchers for publishing their data in a FAIR manner. New research evaluation metrics could be developed based on e.g. the number of publications attached with PIDs, data download and reuse figures within and outside the institute and repository, and data citations, which would all lead to recognition. Data citations should be seen as equally important as publication citations. However, metrics need to be considered carefully as “*you get what you measure*”. Complying with requirements set by the funder and publisher, as well as organisational data policies, can affect the researcher’s reputation and serve as merit. Complying with requirements set by the FAIR principles will in addition lead to increased data quality. FAIR data adherence could be part of the evaluation criteria of researchers/staff, by being included in the HR review process. Another incentivising measure that came up in an interview is a reward system for researchers based on a system of points assigned for good quality research outputs generated in annual bonuses.

Develop clear requirements for data sharing and FAIR compliance (v)

Getting the parameters right for requirements and structures on various levels is essential for incentivising research based on the FAIR Principles. EU-level activities should push the national-level agendas and have a direct influence on funder requirements and organisational data policies. It is also seen as important for the requirements to be inductive and in line with reality to promote researchers to be FAIR compliant. Stronger requirements are also brought up as being highly incentivising for driving the FAIR agenda, e.g. complying with the FAIR principles is a requirement for receiving research funding or for acquiring a PhD position. A thoroughly planned data management plan is also seen as an important step for meeting the demands set by the FAIR principles. If the documentation methods, metadata standards to be used and publishing and data sharing practices are not planned for from the very beginning of the research project, it can be impossible to meet the FAIR requirements at the end of the project. Hence, requiring a Data Management Plan (DMP), investing in follow-ups throughout the research project, as well as offering support and tools, such as machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) and integrations using Data Stewardship Wizard or DMPonline, are essential components for realising FAIR compliant research. MaDMPs aim to make the DMPs interoperable, automated and increasingly standardised, and consequently, this will ease work and information flow between the researcher, support personnel as well as service providers.

Foster a cultural change towards FAIR research (vi)

There is a call for a cultural change to make the necessary change happen towards increased FAIR-compliant research and for researchers to understand the importance of FAIR and open science. Good data management practices and FAIR should be an embedded element of everyday research and published data should be treated as a research output similar to publications. Decisions need to be made at all levels regarding how the funding should be distributed to cover the additional practices required for FAIR-compliant research.

Communicate best practices (vii)

Related to cultural change is the demand for changes in communication practices, where recommendations and best practices play a huge role. Best practices are seen as a key driving force when it comes to making researchers comply with the FAIR principles, but also in influencing the change towards increased FAIR

compliance. Providing recommendations is an easy option to help researchers e.g. find databases for publishing their data and to learn about disciplinary-specific practices for being FAIR compliant. Communication also plays a huge role as an incentive; not only to communicate what FAIR is but also to share success stories with peers. Organisations should bring out and highlight success stories by researchers targeted at other researchers, to bring the discussions to a practical level and make them relatable.

3.2.2 Identified challenges

Incentives may try to tackle several challenges identified in the study. Several of the challenges below are direct quotes from the interviewees.

Lack of resources

- Not enough resources and there are not enough people to provide training and/or to receive training.
- Additional funding should be made available for publishing research data in a FAIR manner. Funded data stewards could be a way to accomplish this.
- “Researchers are to be supported by data-steward-services to assure that the researcher can concentrate on their domain.”
- Data sharing projects may initially focus on the country level but are also required to take international interoperability into account.
- Funders may provide additional resources based upon properly published (FAIR) data.
- The focus should be on the provisioning of new (meta)data, rather than spending a lot of time and energy on making old data FAIR.

Communication issues

- Confusing concepts and lack of knowledge:
 - “FAIR is a policy-level term, related to a set of Principles. It is not a set of clearly defined implementation standards. Thanks to several implementations, we see more and more recommendations on how to interpret the Principles and how to implement data-sharing and data-visiting projects.
 - “FAIR Principles GDPR and Access & Authorisation Control are all concepts that need to be taken into account. The combination of these concepts can be perceived as complex in data-exchange projects.
 - “We notice that terms such as ‘FAIR’ and ‘Open science’ are currently relatively unknown among the average researcher.
 - “Lack of good data management planning has a negative impact on FAIR data sharing/publishing/ reuse of data.”
 - “Researchers have not understood the importance of data management planning”.
 - “Metadata inclusion is perceived as difficult by the majority of researchers.”
 - There is a tendency to “water down” the FAIR principles as often machine-actionability of (meta)data is not included as a strict requirement for FAIRness.
- The challenge of communication:

- The main challenge is to make researchers aware of the opportunity to exchange research data in a structured and efficient way. Important to communicate that services (at the institute, national and European levels) will be made available to guide them in that process.

Legal challenges

- “Problems with [a] licence because it is related to legal issues.”
- “Researchers are concerned about copyright, licensing and personal data as research data, which means legal and ethical aspects of research. They have no separate training in these topics. These are very complicated for them.”
- “We have a lot of laws that regulate the data use and sharing. We recommend institutions to have support for these laws and GDPR etc.”
- “We try to do open data, but you can't just put it on the Internet and say hey, here it is because then somebody might come after you and say that you can't do that. It has become more difficult to do it, but you can always strive for it.”

Funding issues

- Funding openness:
 - Open and/or Free Data is not equal to FAIR data as FAIR data is defined as “Accessible under predefined conditions.”
 - "In the case of Open Science, the payer is usually a taxpayer, not [a] commercial organisation."
 - "Open Data is not necessarily Free Data”
- Funding infrastructure:
 - Institutes at the local level should work together in defining and implementing the required infrastructure for researchers at the national and European levels.
 - Funders could play a role by rewarding best practices, for instance by assigning extra funds for good data stewardship.
- Funding resources for data publishing
- Funding support staff
- Communication about funding

Policies and Requirements

- “No policy name is used, but we have funding principles, guidelines for applicants, and funding terms. In a way, these are policy papers in an international context.”
- “Complying with the FAIR principles is not a requirement, rather a recommendation.”
- “National requirements need to match European requirements.”
- “It is not possible to follow all international activities, but we follow for example Science Europe and the Commission's framework program funding.”
- “The upcoming National Open Science Strategy is stating that the research data must be FAIR compliant.”

- “We have bits and pieces in place, a holistic strategy is something that will be done most likely early next year. We are also hands-on working on connected projects.”
- “The significance of these guidelines, exhortations and recommendations of EC are also quite obvious, but changes do not take effect immediately, require time and a certain amount of momentum, such as copyright law.”

Discipline differences

- “Researchers from data-intensive science fields do not ask questions about FAIR, as they could not practise the field without knowledge about FAIR data.”
- “Biodiversity, remote sensing, environmental data and some social sciences, have long experience with sharing data openly and are becoming FAIRer. They are more interested in the logic and how things are done, not specifically in FAIR.”
- An example of the differences between disciplines is the huge variation in the time needed for data curation:
 - “90% of the workload is organising the data. Which is the reason why I am interested in data standardisation so this 90% can turn to 20% and we get more efficient time to work with the data.”
 - “50/50, maybe even more than half of his time is going into data curation.”
 - “Data curation is fairly quick if you do it immediately and the systems are in place.”

Rewarding and recognition

- “We recommend to not only reward an activity, but rather to reward activities that generate value.”
- “Open and FAIR data should not be rewarded separately, but we recommend that a responsible evaluation mechanism should be in place to qualify the (meta)data.”
- “If research data citations would become equally important as publication citations, it would be a valuable merit.”

4. Community engagement

4.1 Ambitions and approach

This part of the deliverable focuses on the outcome of stakeholder engagement efforts. The stakeholder engagement aims to provide a deeper insight into the current state of play regarding FAIR and Open Science developments in the region and to ultimately achieve policy alignment among our countries. To meet this end, we organised a virtual workshop targeted at community stakeholders and policymakers on 9 May 2022. The workshop highlighted both indirect and policy-driven FAIR incentives which are efficient components for driving a change towards the increased quality of research with the help of the FAIR principles. The workshop consisted of two parts; 1. presentations of the findings from the qualitative study on FAIR incentives and 2. an interactive session, allowing the participants to influence the FAIR incentives to be promoted. The discussions of the workshop are summarised in subchapter 4.2 of this deliverable. A complete list of all contributors to this chapter is found as an appendix in [table A1](#).

4.2 Feedback from key stakeholders

Overall conclusions of workshop discussions

The workshop attracted 45 participants from a variety of stakeholders and countries. The discussions were rich and generated valuable insights into our work on FAIR incentives. The participants were unanimous on many discussion points, e.g.:

- Incentives are an important driver for cultural change.
- Both ministries of education and science and RFOs should work towards gradually implementing strict requirements on FAIR compliance.

- Data standards, qualifications, certifications, and self-assessments should be developed for overall consistency.
- Changes should be incorporated at all levels.
- Overall communication on FAIR and the advantages of FAIR needs to be improved.
- FAIR awareness is crucial for the successful implementation of all of the above!

Policies

Policies on FAIR data are currently being intensely worked on at different levels within the region. In addition to covering the FAIR Principles in the relevant policies, services also need to correspond to the principles. EU and international level compatibility is important when making national-level decisions on FAIR. There is a clear need and desire to work on national policies collaboratively across borders to harmonise the policies. However, due to national differences, some varying approaches need to be applied.

Cultural change

It became evident through the discussions that the top-ranked components for achieving a research culture based on FAIR are:

1. Raising researcher awareness of best practices
2. Having adequate support services in place at organisations

The workshop participants also supported those topics during the discussion on incentive funding for data curation & sharing. The results showed that the top priority is to give resources for support services assisting researchers in their everyday work, allowing them to manage their data well.

Researchers need straightforward instructions, guidance, examples, and support to reach the requirements to produce FAIR data. We identified four ways to support researchers in their efforts:

- Have subject-specific data stewards available.
- Have centralised support services such as Competence Centres at organisations.
- Organise education and training for researchers about good data management and, most importantly, offer it from early-on career stages.
- Offer easy-to-use tools and infrastructure for researchers that make complying with FAIR effortless. It is everyone's (institutional, national, EU & EOSC, domain communities) responsibility to organise sustainable infrastructure for sharing and publishing data.

To increase the FAIR uptake, a foundational layer has to be in place. This layer was perceived to consist of securely and sustainably built RDM services supporting interoperability. User-friendliness of the FAIR-enabling tools and services makes it incentivising to use them. Acceptance by the researchers is paramount to realise a cultural change. Also, some top-level pushes were seen as an efficient mechanism to leverage a change in the research community. That is best achieved by having funding available for FAIR-compliant research and showcasing how FAIR data can lead to high-end research.

To speed up the cultural change we need a stronger emphasis on the "make it required" part, founded by a combination of easy-to-use services and concrete rewards for "good behaviour". That research is FAIR should be part of research metrics, and we should provide researchers with good examples and guidelines to follow.

Research funding & related challenges

Having part of the funding earmarked for making the data FAIR is desirable. The challenge is in justly deciding the amount of funding to be set aside for this part of the research work, as some scientific domains can be very data-intensive and others less so. Another difficulty lies in reaching out to the researchers when a change in data management is requested by the funder. Training and practical guides on legal requirements and research ethics lower the barriers to adhering to open and FAIR research practices. Additionally, the implementation of a system based on data stewards is needed to further the FAIR development. These support services cater for sufficient resourcing at the organisational level. DMPs should be made a requirement for funding and thus help make data FAIR by design.

Monitoring & rewards

The Research Performing Organisations need to include the FAIR principles in their policies and monitor and reward the reuse of data. Peer recognition within the community is seen as an important incentive for FAIR compliance. The DMP should be a part of the research assessment. However, we must remember that we get what we measure and consciously need to avoid setting the research assessment into a similar position as with the Open Access to publications, where quantity rules over quality. The research communities and learned societies should be involved in defining the metrics and rewarding mechanisms suitable for that specific scientific discipline, together with actors on all levels; institutional, national, EU and funder.

Supporting FAIR data through communication

The best way to raise awareness of FAIR is to offer clarity and showcase it through examples, e.g. in the form of stories on lessons-learnt and practical guides. FAIR-enthusiastic researchers should raise awareness among their fellow researchers and change the system from within. More effective dissemination should occur from within disciplines where FAIR is already part of the operating culture and where the benefits have been recognised and realised. Communication is the pivotal activity in which all stakeholders need to be involved. More focus should generally be devoted to communicating the benefits and purposes of the FAIR Principles, along with clear uptake strategies.

5. Accelerating the uptake of FAIR through incentives

In this chapter, we present the findings from the qualitative study on FAIR incentives with the ambition to foster a change in the way FAIR is being valued and understood and to provide insight into the perceived benefits and expected impact of increased FAIR uptake in research. We first introduce two FAIR Archetypes with opposite perceptions of FAIR - The FAIR Newbie and the FAIR Master. With these archetypes, we wish to showcase different behaviours as examples to ultimately be able to leverage a change in how the FAIR principles are perceived in scientific circles. Next, we provide recommendations for relevant stakeholders on the next steps to take to cater for the increased uptake of FAIR. The relevant stakeholders with tailor-made recommendations are Research Performing Organisations (RPO), Service and Infrastructure Providers, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), and Ministries of Education and Science. Last, we present the expected impacts on science in the Nordic and Baltic countries as a result of FAIR implementations on various levels.

5.2 FAIR archetypes

All of the quotes originate from the interviews.

Building archetypes is a method used in product, service, etc. design projects with a user experience (UX) approach. These archetypes are based on information collected, in this case via interviews. Archetypes help us discover behavioural patterns to predict how a person will behave or react. Our goal is to influence people's behaviour and even change the culture towards adopting FAIR principles. To do this, we need a better understanding of the current patterns of thought and behaviour.

The archetypes are not real persons. We decided to build two archetypes, representing extremes in the attitudes towards and awareness of the FAIR principles. Master answers to quotes like: “Highlighting success stories and benefits is an important factor here” and “champions should be highlighted as role models, individual researchers, research groups, but also research areas” (figure 5).

We use them to explore:

- What can we learn from the Masters?
- How can we motivate Newbies to become Masters?

Figure 5: FAIR Newbie vs FAIR Master

5.2.1 FAIR Newbie

The Newbie thinks that FAIR is a requirement emanating from outside of the research community.

- “[The] Research Council started to request [a] data management vision in their applications, and after the first six months of the projects, a DMP had to be attached to the proposal.”

The Newbie has not noticed whether it is the own organisation or the funder that requires FAIR data.

- (Is there a data policy at the university?) "I'm pretty sure there is one, but I haven't read it."

The Newbie believes no one knows how to follow FAIR principles.

- "FAIR data, metadata and vocabularies are too young concepts. Most people are still afraid of giving out data, nobody wants to work with metadata (boring, time-intense)." "Had to learn the basics about FAIR when writing the DMP. The language used in the FAIR principles can be tricky and you would have to know a lot about data management to fully understand what is meant by the principles. It would be helpful to have some real-case examples equipped with the principles, ideally some discipline-specific guidelines. The FAIR principles made me confused without examples

from my own field."

The Newbie has no experience of benefits.

- "If I were to make the non-sensitive data available, what would make me do it? An assistant, it's very boring work to describe data, and I have many other more fun things to do."

The Newbie demands clear guidance and more support.

- "Useful with planning would be support from professionals in the same field and, for example, from researchers who have led projects where data management has worked well and from which good practice could be modelled." "Having support and guidance would be an incentive that people will appreciate."

The Newbie needs more money.

- "People will publish openly if there is money for it somewhere."

The Newbie thinks that no one can understand or use my data.

- "Would not publish raw data because nobody would make any sense out of them." "Serious concern that when we make our data open, others may interpret it in the wrong way."

The Newbie does not use data created by others.

- "When there is an experiment in mind, I don't see it in a way that I could utilise someone else's data in it."

5.2.2 FAIR Master

The Master thinks that FAIR is an integral part of good research practice.

- "Science is by definition open."

The Master knows that organisations and funders require FAIR data.

- "Institution has a template for DMPs, their data policies are connected to that."

The Master believes that everybody knows FAIR principles.

- "Most people have heard about FAIR principles" "everybody supports the FAIR principles."

The Master has their own experience of benefits.

- "When people begin to use your data, it advertises your project and has a big impact."

The Master utilises existing services and creates new tools if needed.

- "Topics were gathered to create a metadata schema with generic and domain-specific and build taxonomies of the descriptive metadata. The prototype of the concept data registry was created."

The Master needs recognition for good work done.

- "If research data citations would become equally important as publication citations, it would be a valuable merit."

The Master argues that articles without data can not be trusted.

- "It is kind of a signal of honesty that there is my data, you can check out what I have done."

The Master uses data created by others.

- "Yeah, I think so. Because we use what's called corpora, large collections of text, so somebody else has compiled it already, and then you do your research on that."

5.3 Cultural change

In the interview analysis phase, cultural change was a frequently mentioned topic and suggested as something that has to occur for FAIR practices to become a norm within research. For a long time, many researchers kept their research data to themselves and even until this day they meet the opening and sharing research data with scepticism, suspicion, and even fear of someone else profiting from their efforts. A change in research culture can reverse that kind of thinking.

5.3.1 Interview findings related to cultural change

Some interviewees used the exact term cultural change, while others described the essential nature of the term.

- “Researchers need to be enlightened in their everyday work to do good data management and consequently produce fair data.”
- “Culture change is needed to happen in research communities as well as within research infrastructures to get this done.”
- “Cultural change – infrastructure is one side, but best practices/piloting should be part of the system.”; “it needs to be part of the daily process or system.” [FAIR]
- “Cultural change is well promoted by open science groups established in our country. The goal by 2025 is for all aspects of open science to be part of everyday life in the work of different actors. We need to proceed with open science issues at the same pace with international cooperation.”
- “Yes. The transformation needs a combination of requirements, notching and friendly culture change. Only good will does not work.”
- “Urging would be needed that data and metadata would be made open and the percentage to rise, but that requires additional resources. For data to be FAIR, attention should be paid to it throughout the data lifecycle.”
- “Open science is seen as a hoax.”

Some interviewees shared their thoughts on data sharing that reflects the existing research culture regarding research data:

- “Worried about how they can get the most out of their data before sharing it.”
- “In the Horizon training, it is said there should be no embargo periods anymore. As soon as the article is published, the data needs to be published as well. This worries researchers, they want to use the data to produce more articles themselves.”
- “Some colleagues are sceptical about opening up data because there is a fear that someone will analyse something about it that they would like to analyse.”
- “Generate new data, we do not give the data away before we make complete use for our own research.”
- “Data is [a]strong asset and if you give it away before having extracted everything out from it, you cannot get the maximum value.”

- “Some think this is my data, and don't want to share it before it is published. All scientists know that the publication is important but sharing data is not that common even though it is improving.”

There are many interdependent activities to consider to change research culture and make FAIR data a part of everyday research, focusing strongly on community development and incentives. Infrastructure, user experience, FAIR knowledge, communities, incentives, and policies are all significant factors. When focusing on a certain activity the big picture should always be in mind, as all activities rely on the capability of others.

5.3.2 Theory of change model and diffusion of innovation theory

Based on the composed findings from the studies for this deliverable, several recommendations have been developed, categorised according to the strategy for culture change model mentioned in 1.2, with specific actions targeted toward different types of stakeholders. While categorising the findings from our study according to these levels, we realised that the one relevant level was missing. Thus, we introduced the basement level, from where the change in research culture needs to start - Awareness-raising - Make it understandable (figure 6).

Figure 6: Theory of change model including the basement level - awareness-raising

As brought up in chapter 1.2, the diffusion of innovation theory shows how people generally accept innovations. Human capital is crucial for making a cultural change happen. By combining the two models, we get a comprehensive understanding of what it takes to achieve a cultural change (figure 7).

Figure 7: Diffusion of innovation theory (Roggers, E., 1962) and the Theory of change model (Nosek B., 2019) combined

Infrastructure is what makes it possible and also forms the base level of the pyramid. Innovators are the smallest adopter category that can take advantage of new infrastructure or participate in building one. Those are people who are actively looking for new ideas, see the bigger picture and are ready to take risks. It shows that just one level of the pyramid cannot affect the change in a culture shift, but can impact a specific target group.

The user interface and experience, as well as the knowledge of the new activity, make it simple to understand and use. This level corresponds to early adopters, who, according to Roggers, have the highest level of opinion leadership among the adopter categories. It demonstrates that when something is simple and easy to understand, more people are willing to adopt it; however, infrastructure and know-how alone are insufficient.

Making it normative and rewarding are major parts of cultural change when the highest number of new adapters are ready to join the movement. The emphasis lies on incentives that help to convince the group of late adopters. The social aspect of community engagement, as well as the benefits of incentives, are important factors in the change. Here we can also see that previously mentioned groups – innovators and early adopters - play a key role in community building. They can share ideas, benefits, and experience and take leadership positions in their communities.

The final adopter group – laggards – is addressed by the policy aspect and making it mandatory. When nothing else works to persuade a target group, a set of specific rules must be followed. Regulations and ensuring standards, general management, and overall guidance for people are all important aspects of

policy. Mandatory requirements can be the main motivation for a specific target group, but the policy itself provides the new practice with direction, consistency, accountability, efficiency, and clarity.

5.4 Recommendations to Stakeholders

Below all recommendations to stakeholders are compiled and categorised according to the relevant level with one table for each level. Within each level the target group, e.g. RFOs, is used as a secondary categorisation, denoted by columns. The columns are coherent between the tables, so all recommendations for a specific category can easily be identified across the tables.

Table 4: Make it required

"Make it required"			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Include the FAIR Principles in an official Data Policy of the organisation.</p> <p>Monitor the amount of data/number of datasets and data publications produced and/or published by the institute or repository using a PID.</p>	<p>Build services that are interoperable and secure. Offer sustainable infrastructure that supports research</p>	<p>Follow EU-level developments on FAIR and include these in national-level decisions.</p> <p>Require FAIR compliance and a DMP to be in place as conditions to receive funding.</p> <p>Monitor the amount of data/datasets and data publications produced and/or published by the beneficiary using a PID.</p> <p>Promote a general "cultural change" towards FAIR data and assure proper funding of the changes.</p>	<p>Follow EU-level developments on FAIR and include these in national-level decisions.</p> <p>Include the FAIR Principles in relevant policies. Include a notion that the services and infrastructure should correspond to the FAIR Principles.</p> <p>Monitor the uptake of FAIR practices at the national level, ideally in a way that is comparable internationally.</p>

Table 5: Make it rewarding

"Make it rewarding"			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Consider putting a reward system in place for incentivising FAIR research outputs.</p> <p>Include FAIR data adherence as part of the evaluation criteria of researchers/staff, to be included in the HR review process.</p> <p>Monitor the amount of data/datasets and data publications produced and/or published by the institute or repository using a PID.</p> <p>Monitor the reuse of data within and outside the institute or repository.</p> <p>Update the merit system with new research evaluation metrics, better aligned with the requirements of FAIR research practices. Set requirements of FAIR compliance as a condition for advancing in the research career.</p>	<p>Motivate data depositing by offering long-term central data storage</p> <p>Make metadata easy and understandable so that depositing data is simple.</p> <p>Provide features that motivate the end-user to do FAIR research, e.g. by enabling articles to be citable based on re-used data along with a description of methods.</p>	<p>Assign proper funding covering FAIR data management and needed resources. Consider setting aside a dedicated pot of funding for publishing FAIR data.</p> <p>Monitor the amount of data/number of datasets and data publications produced and/or published by the beneficiary using a PID.</p> <p>Promote a general "cultural change" towards FAIR data and assure proper funding of the changes.</p>	<p>Monitor the uptake of FAIR practices at the national level.</p>

Table 6: Make it normative

"Make it normative"			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Provide researchers with concrete examples of best practices and practical, tailor-made recommendations for different scientific domains on becoming increasingly FAIR and how FAIR data can lead to high-end research. Explain that "FAIR data" is not equal to "Open and Free data".</p> <p>Show that FAIR is part of data safety.</p> <p>Evaluate, which data is worth making FAIR, and on what level (selection is part of the norm)</p>	<p>Provide hands-on descriptions and clear instructions related to FAIR.</p> <p>Provide courses on how to make data FAIR.</p> <p>Provide easy-to-use tools and provide advantages of FAIR aspects to the researchers</p>	<p>Promote a general "cultural change" towards FAIR data and assure proper funding of the changes.</p> <p>Require FAIRness of data as a condition to receive research grants.</p>	<p>Promote a "cultural change" by introducing training in the curriculum for future generations of researchers on FAIR data management and assuring proper funding for the changed data management requirements.</p>

Table 7: Make it easy

"Make it easy"			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Consider a Data Competence Center (DCC) to support the researchers and other staff in adhering to the</p>	<p>Deploy the use of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs).</p>	<p>Assign proper funding covering FAIR data management and needed resources.</p> <p>Consider setting aside</p>	<p>Promote a "cultural change" by training future generations of researchers on FAIR data management and</p>

<p>organisation's data policy. Hire data stewards as part of the DCC activities.</p> <p>Promote using Machine Actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and DMP tools such as the Data Stewardship Wizard¹², DMPonline¹³ and EasyDMP¹⁴.</p> <p>Cater for sufficient resources for support (also technical), services and tools for conducting FAIR-compliant research.</p> <p>Train Data Stewards to assist with Persistent Identifiers, the inclusion of metadata and making (meta)data machine-actionable.</p> <p>Establish good practical guides on managing data, and complying with legal requirements and research-ethical guidelines.</p>	<p>Ensure that the service supports interoperability and allows rich metadata descriptions and machine-actionability.</p> <p>Share vocabularies, ontologies and other FAIR implementation choices within and between organisations and repositories.</p> <p>Develop domain-centric guides for researchers on how to FAIRify specific types of research data.</p> <p>Provide sustainable services for controlled vocabularies, e.g. SKOSMOS hosted services like the one at the Finnish National Library¹⁵.</p>	<p>a dedicated pot of funding for publishing FAIR data.</p> <p>Promote using Machine Actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and DMP tools such as the Data Stewardship Wizard, DMPonline or EasyDMP.</p>	<p>assure proper funding for the changed data management requirements.</p> <p>Provide adequate resources for organisations to supply necessary training, support staff and tools for FAIR data management.</p> <p>Provide training on legal and research-ethical aspects of data management/sharing.</p>
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¹² Data Stewardship Wizard. (2018). *Data stewardship wizard*. <https://ds-wizard.org/>

¹³ DMPonline. (2022). *Plan to make data work for you*. <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

¹⁴ Sigma2. (2022). *EasyDMP – NIRD Data Planning*. <https://www.sigma2.no/data-planning>

¹⁵ National Library of Finland.(2022). Finto. <http://finto.fi/en/>

Table 8: Make it possible

"Make it possible"			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Cater for sufficient resources for support (including technical), services and tools for conducting FAIR-compliant research.</p> <p>Provide adequate support services and training for researchers that coincide with the additional demands on producing FAIR-compliant research and ensure researcher awareness of the support in place.</p> <p>Create inner "informant" networks of FAIR masters who disseminate information among colleagues.</p>	<p>Base your activities on sustainable funding and organisational models.</p> <p>Ensure that the service supports interoperability and allows rich metadata descriptions and machine-actionability.</p> <p>Share vocabularies, ontologies and other FAIR implementation choices within and between organisations and repositories.</p> <p>Provide sustainable repositories.</p> <p>Provide researchers with an overview of the most important considerations when dealing with your infrastructure (e.g. the possibilities of backing up data on servers).</p>	<p>Promote a general "cultural change" towards FAIR data and assure proper funding of the changes.</p> <p>Provide easy-to-use DMP templates and guidance. Evaluate and give feedback about data management planning.</p> <p>Allow data management experience to count as merit when applying for funding and monitor FAIR compliance.</p>	<p>Provide adequate resources for organisations to supply necessary training, support staff and tools for FAIR data management.</p> <p>Incentivise a platform where RFOs and RPOs can discuss and share experiences related to FAIR.</p> <p>Provide adequate funding for basic FAIR infrastructure.</p> <p>Fund data steward positions in academia.</p>

Table 9: Make it understandable and raise awareness

“Make it understandable and raise awareness”			
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Service and Infrastructure Providers	Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Ministries
<p>Provide researchers with examples of best practices and practical, tailor-made recommendations for different scientific domains on how to become increasingly FAIR. Explain that "FAIR data" is not equal to "Open and Free data".</p> <p>Provide a single starting point for FAIR Newbies with easily understandable and findable practical information. The specifics could follow after to avoid overwhelming the researcher with information.</p> <p>Develop direct and easy-to-use communicating channels between the researchers and support personnel.</p> <p>Make an "inventory" of researchers already practising FAIR and</p>	<p>Raise awareness of data management and FAIR data.</p> <p>Show what your data repository and services can offer to researchers.</p>	<p>Recommend and promote data repositories that are acceptable to the funder.</p> <p>Structure DMP templates in consultation with the research community, making them easy to understand and instructional.</p> <p>Demand DMPs for all applications to help make FAIR data by design and make the DMP part of the assessment.</p>	<p>Raise awareness of the bigger picture - what is good science, which are the benefits of FAIR.</p> <p>Create a sense of urgency, and emphasise that things are changing.</p>

<p>work with them to spread the idea. Make the researcher's work as simple as possible. If everything is clear (how to make data FAIR), many more will do it.</p>			
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5.5 Expected impact of increased FAIR uptake in the region

The incentives introduced in this deliverable act both as carrots and sticks to increase the uptake of FAIR use in the region. The goal is that the relevant stakeholders, such as ministries, research performing organisations, research funding organisations, and service/infrastructure providers take action to increase the uptake of FAIR.

It is prevalent that the whole region follows EU-level development and that actions about FAIR compliance form an integral part of national-level decisions and relevant policies. E.g., when FAIR compliance and DMPs are required as conditions to receive funding, it directly impacts awareness-raising and understanding of FAIR data management. However, to significantly increase the uptake of FAIR, we need to take the next step from raising awareness and promoting understanding to start acting towards an environment that makes it easy and rewarding for researchers to follow the FAIR principles.

Including the FAIR Principles as an integral part of organisational data policies has several positive impacts on research and gets us one step closer to an imperative cultural change in research. Organisational FAIR data policies have, e.g., a motivational effect on researchers when it comes to complying with the FAIR principles and also increase both the data quality and the quality and impact of research as a whole when planning and adhering to the FAIR principles from the very start of the research endeavour.

Promoting the use of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMP), for example, facilitates easy and seamless information workflow and enables the integration between systems by the research performing organisations, service providers and research funding organisations. That supports the adoption of FAIR in the everyday work of researchers and enhances communication between the researcher and support staff, which in turn eases planning and risk management.

There is clearly strong support from the research community to strengthen the efforts for FAIR and Open Science. When this is reflected properly in the budget negotiations, research effectiveness improves through enhanced support for FAIR data management and open science to the researchers.

Allocating resources to support the cultural change towards FAIR data management impacts the whole of research - supporting the community and the researchers. That includes providing adequate resourcing for research-performing organisations responsible for offering training, support, services and tools for researchers. Increased resources for training on applying FAIR in research increases awareness and skills development. Data quality, trust, and research transparency are all expected to benefit from increased support for FAIR research data management. The same applies to providing adequate funding for infrastructure providers, who enable, e.g., researchers to publish FAIR data.

Centralising the support efforts at RPOs to a Data Competence Centre (DCC) makes it easier to cater for comprehensive support coverage and provides a good overview of available support modes. A sufficient number of data stewards, contributing with domain-specific expertise, provide researchers with the support needed to embed the FAIR principles in all stages of the research data life cycle.

The researchers' motivation to comply with the FAIR data management practices increases when recognition of FAIR efforts is part of the merit system. FAIR data publications, data reuse, and other endeavours related to FAIR data management should be monitored and valued not only by the RFOs but also by the RPOs, e.g. in hiring processes. These will also positively affect the cultural change, where FAIR data is valued and production supported. As a bonus, the data quality will generally increase with adherence to good FAIR data management practices. In case, e.g. data reuse and PID usage for data and publications are monitored, the RPO can get an increased understanding of the level of the researchers' data management skills and how well publicly funded research is openly and persistently available.

Service and infrastructure providers also have a huge role to play in making an impact on the uptake of FAIR. If infrastructures are truly FAIR compliant and easy-to-use, this will help and motivate researchers to use them and consequently support them to comply with the FAIR requirements. Infrastructures should pay attention to interoperability, allow rich metadata including relevant semantic artefacts and

machine-actionability, offer PIDs, and help with licensing data. It is vital that service providers also support the users in the process if needed.

6. Conclusions

Incentives are an important driver for cultural change. The necessary changes should be incorporated at all levels, and all stakeholders have a role to play in advancing the uptake of FAIR research practices. A common thread throughout this study has been the realisation that there is a need to raise proper awareness among researchers on FAIR and its values as best practices and through communication with FAIR advocates. Another common denominator throughout the study has been the importance of adequate support services and a rewarding system at organisations for complying with the FAIR Principles. Accelerating the cultural change calls for a stronger emphasis on the “make it required” part coupled with a combination of easy-to-use services and concrete rewards for FAIR compliance. To leverage the change, proper funding is crucial, to begin with. Coupled with the findings made in this study and by creating a sense of urgency among the research communities that things are changing, the situation will evidently change and lead to a research society where FAIR research practices are the norm.

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Appendices

Table A1: External stakeholders contributing to chapter 4. Community engagement

Name	Affiliation
Tuula Hämäläinen	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
Tiiu Tarkpea	Tartu University Library
Pirjo Kontkanen	University of Helsinki
Ginte Medzvieckaite	Vilnius University Library
Tomi Rosti	University of Eastern Finland
Joakim Philipson	Stockholm University
Philipp Conzett	UiT The Arctic University of Norway
Mari Kleemola	FSD/CESSDA, Tampere University
Heleri Inno	University of Tartu
Joakim Philipson	Stockholm University
Sanna Marttinen	Finnish Partnership for Research Institutes (Tulanet)
Eva Stensköld	Riksbankens Jubileumsfond
Gudbjorg Andrea Jonsdottir	University of Iceland
Nina-Mari Salminen	Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)
Nikoline Dohm Lauridsen	Technical University of Denmark (DTU)
Marjolein Thunnissen	MAX IV Lund University
Anne Sofie Fink Kjeldgaard	Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC)
Ingrid Heggland	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
Mareike Buss	Copenhagen Business School
Lars Ove Dragsted	University of Copenhagen
John Renner Hansen	Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC)

Harri Hautala	Academy of Finland
Karsten Kryger Hansen	Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC)
Edvards Kuks	Ministry of Education and Science of Latvia
Margaret Louise Fotland	University of Oslo
Trond Kvamme	Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt)
Bodil Agasøster	Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt)
Pauline L'Henaff	Health-RI
Harri Pitkänen	Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)
Karen Sofie Hytteballe Ibanez	Technical University of Denmark (DTU)
Ingmārs Kreišmanis	Riga Stradins University
Darren Spruce	MAX IV Lund University Laboratory
Kotar Mojca	University of Ljubljana
Archana Bidargaddi	Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt)
Magnus Klingberg	MAX IV Lund University
Romas Baronas	Research Council of Lithuania
Sarmite Mickevica	Ministry of Education and Science of Latvia
Birna Gunnarsdottir	University of Iceland
Katrine Flindt Holmstrand	Technical University of Denmark
Sveinung Gundersen	ELIXIR Norway, University of Oslo

Appendix 2: Quotations from interview notes

Lack of resources

- "Not enough resources, not enough people training"
- "Funding body to allocate money / earmarked money for publishing data: e.g. a number of months to support the publication of data or for example, an outside person to support publishing/ opening or a part-time person who handles data issues for several projects (e.g. 2 months of the year would look after your project data issues)."
- "Building functional services requires resources."
- "Problematic to think that researchers must do everything - dominant way of thinking today"; "waste of resources that they should learn it well [to make data FAIR open] because they should be doing research."
- "Work [with data sharing] needs to be done on a country level to ensure that the capacities are in place."
- "If the project would receive additional resources, e.g. additional funding if the data is published well." [Incentives for FAIR agenda]
- "Lack of time and energy to clean the data to get it ready for sharing."
- "Changing data to be FAIR is a long process, projects are long, collecting data takes time."

Communication issues

- "FAIR is a policy-level term, there it fits in well. When the term itself leaves many things undefined, it is best suited to the policy level."
- "FAIR, policies and GDPR came about the same time and can get confused at times."
- "FAIR and open science as terms are fairly unknown."
- "Lack of good data management planning has an impact on FAIR data sharing/publishing & opening."
- "Researchers have not understood the importance of data management planning."
- "Metadata is perceived as difficult"
- "Guidance is not clear."
- "Getting people to realise that there are some changes and that they need to do something to/with the data."

Funding issues

- **Funding openness:**
 - "Open is only open when someone is willing to pay for it."
 - "In the case of Open Science, the payer is usually a taxpayer, not [a] commercial organisation."
 - "Openness is not always free, it requires funding to be open."
- **Funding infrastructure**
 - "Universities need to sponsor this (storage) infrastructure in order to make this change happen."
 - "The funders should not fund the infrastructure. The main costs should be covered by the universities for equality purposes (such as data storage)"
 - "infrastructure that seeks to support research and on the other hand, we also need funding to maintain the infrastructure."

- “Even internally there are payment requirements for the sensitive data storage, so there is [a] need for better funding solutions.”
- **Funding (resources for) data publishing:**
 - “Funding body to allocate money/earmarked money for publishing data: e.g. number of months to support the publication of data or for example, an outside person to support publishing/opening or a part-time person who handles data issues for several projects (e.g. 2 months of the year would look after your project data issues).”
 - “Yes, resources are planned but not through the approach of adding additional funds for data management – this is not sustainable.”
 - “Critical of the gap in between the requirements of EU or funders to keep your data for a long time, but without the willingness to fund data curation after publication.”
- **Funding support staff:**
 - “Main issue is the financial part of it, as in a lot of other countries. Data stewardship is expensive, and the government is often times a bit vague on the implementation part. [The] government seems to be hoping that the institutions take care of the financial issues themselves.”
- **Knowledge about funding:**
 - “Researchers don’t know about all the associated and estimated costs [of RDM] and cannot easily put them into a plan.”
 - “The Research Council expects this for the funding decisions and includes it in the overhead, but they are expecting many other things to belong to this overhead, so it is not that clear.”

- **Rewarding and recognition**
 - “We do not only want to reward an activity, but rather something that generate value.”
 - “openness and FAIR should not be rewarded separately, but a responsible evaluation mechanism should be set up”
 - “no merit in making data FAIR”
 - “If research data citations would become equally important as publication citations, it would be a valuable merit.”

Figure A2: positive statements (AtlasTI output)

Figure A3: negative statements (AtlasTI output)

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Glossary

Term	Explanation
maDMP	A machine-actionable Data Management Plan, i.e. a plan in a formal format, e.g. ADI, where the information can be retrieved by a computer without manual intervention.

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